

Quantum Circuits, HyperCubeHarmonic, and Improvisation: a Case Study of a Remote Networked Performance of the Female Laptop Orchestra

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Abstract. *The HyperCubeHarmonic—an interactive 4D virtual instrument inspired by the Rubik’s Cube, with its sonic output shaped by data from a custom-designed quantum logic gate implemented by a quantum circuit—was used as the basis for a Networked Music Performance (NMP) titled ‘Telematic City Jam - Glasgow’. This performance was recorded telematically using SonoBus NMP platform, then mixed and mastered for broadcast as part of the Radiophrenia 2025 festival. Here, we describe concept, method, and realisation of that musical piece. The concept and performance demonstrate how quantum computing can be incorporated into NMP, creative music systems and telematic improvisational frameworks.*

1 Introduction

Networked Music Performance (NMP) is a growing area of artistic practice and research based on musicians interacting over the internet to “perform, compose, improvise, teach, and learn music across physical distances” [1]. NMP projects might be synchronous (i.e., musicians are playing together in real-time) or asynchronous (i.e., musicians are exchanging audiovisual content and working on it in their own time). They can also be set up in a way that utilises the usual musician/audience divide or in a way that actively engages the audience. Recently, the field of Networked Musical Performances started to include the suggestions from quantum computing, formalising procedures and fostering new creativity applications, also with the addition of a Rubik’s cube-based musical instrument, the CubeHarmonic [2, 3]. Quantum computing is also used as a source of sonic material, e.g., with the sonification of Rabi oscillations in quantum physics [4], of quantum noise [5], or the development of new synthesizers [6].

A rather theoretical approach to the Networked Music Performance, with a first application of the CubeHarmonic, is described in [2], while an in-detail description of the instrument is proposed in [3]. Here, we describe a specific use of the 4D CubeHarmonic (the HyperCubeHarmonic, HCH), where the rotations are decided ac-

ording to the measurements in a quantum circuit specifically designed for this piece, and then exploited in the framework of a real networked performance, with musicians communicating over internet in real time from different places around the world. We describe a live performance with quantum computing, based on a quantum algorithm for music, and quantum-aided composition.

In particular, here, we focus on a specific experiment of quantum-based Networked Musical Performance developed by the Female Laptop Orchestra (FLO). Here, we outline FLO’s practice-based methodology for implementing telematic performances, present approaches to enhance audience experience through immersive spatialisation and visualisation, and propose methods for archiving distributed performances. The contributions of this work include a novel integration of quantum computation into musical composition. The findings inform future directions that FLO will pursue and provide a framework for incorporating quantum computing in NMP.

The article is organised as follows. In Section 2, we present FLO. In Section 3, we present the core quantum idea, its implementation on the virtual instrument, and the structure of the musical composition. In Section 4, we discuss possible developments in future projects.

2 Female Laptop Orchestra

The Female Laptop Orchestra (FLO), founded in 2014 by [last author], is a groundbreaking music research project that unites female musicians, sound artists, composers, engineers and computer scientists from around the world. FLO thrives on co-located and distributed collaborative music creation and uses NMP as the basis for its artistic activity. Each FLO performance is site-specific and performer-dependent, mixing location-based field recordings, live coding, acoustic instruments, voice, sound synthesis and real-time sound processing using Web Audio APIs and VR environments with audio streams arriving from different global locations (via the internet and mobile

networks). From stereo to immersive 3D audio (and everything in between), FLO redefines ensemble improvisation and telematic collaboration, constantly pushing the boundaries of technology and artistic experimentation. FLO is committed to promoting gender balance in STEM fields where women have historically—and continue to be—underrepresented. The initiative fosters an inclusive and supportive environment that encourages learning, creativity, experimentation and collaboration. FLO aims to amplify diverse narratives, highlighting many different views and experiences through interdisciplinary media, including music, visuals, poetry, movement and technology. As part of this mission, FLO presents projects, delivers talks and conducts workshops to raise awareness of the underrepresentation of women in the sound and music computing fields, as discussed in [7].

Each FLO performance is uniquely site-specific and performer-dependent, reflecting the globally distributed nature of the collective. The audio dimension typically involves a range of practices, including field recordings, acoustic instrumentation, sound synthesis, live coding, Web Audio API platforms, and soundwalks streamed over a 4G/5G network, etc. The visual component usually involves pre-recorded videos by dance artists, and/or real-time visuals generated using VR or software that dynamically responds to different features of the audio. Occasionally, social media platforms are integrated to facilitate ‘audience participation’ in the performance. By bridging time zones, continents, political boundaries and languages, FLO performances explore telematic intercultural collaboration and examine how globally distributed audiences perceive different modalities that such disembodied audio-visual performances (afforded by the network) provide.

Before the COVID-19 pandemic, FLO was already pushing the boundaries of technology and experimentation in ensemble improvisation and telematic collaboration. The remote way of working in the arts became even more prominent with the onset of the pandemic, leading to a plethora of new platforms supporting this kind of artistic production. This, in turn, led to several high-profile performances and talks in which FLO was invited to participate. During the pandemic, FLO developed a framework for Networked Music Performance (NMP) in which the remote audio streams are mixed and spatialised for the ‘in-person’ audience using multichannel/ immersive configurations, whilst the stereo mix, along with the visuals produced in real-time, is streamed to the FLO YouTube channel for the remotely located ‘virtual audience’ [8, 9].

3 The core idea and the structure of the piece

As part of the ongoing exploration into new ways of creative collaboration afforded by the network, FLO conceived a Networked Music Performance titled ‘Telematic City Jam - Glasgow’ which utilised a new instrument, the CubeHarmonic, which is based on the Rubik’s Cube and a quantum circuit and mixes different chords.

We use a quantum circuit, new but loosely inspired by [2], to implement a logic gate, aiming to create pitch variety. In fact, pitches were associated with values 0 or 1, and the results of quantum measurement were mapped back into pitch. The resulting short musical sequences are then played with a virtual instrument, the HyperCubeHarmonic [3], designed by M. Mannone and implemented by T. Yoshino, and recorded. The recordings constituted the starting point for a 3-part remote networked improvisation.

The 3D projection of the HyperCubeHarmonic, a 4D object, is constituted by eight Rubik’s cubes. A rotation on one of them affects the rotation of the nearby cubes. In the implementation of [2], each cube is tuned with a pitch. Thus, there are eight pitches. It is possible to click and play each cube individually, before and after a rotation. The rotations are also user-selected via the interface. The virtual instrument is entirely coded in Mathematica [3].

3.1 The quantum circuit

Let us now present the defined logic gate and its implementation on a quantum circuit. For the sake of simplicity, we focus on three cubes of the HyperCubeHarmonic. We choose to rotate or non-rotate two of them, and the gate tells us whether to rotate the third cube. Thus, our input is the state of two cubes, and the output hints what to do on the third one. The choice of the cubes where to focus on is apt to the user. We chose to indicate the absence of rotation with the logic 1, thus needed the NOT gate (+) to initialize the state as non-rotated. The logic 0 denotes the configuration of the rotated cube. The state *balanced superposition*, implemented with the Hadamard gate (H), denotes indeterminacy, an equal-weight superposition of 0 and 1. To increase musical variety, if both the two inputted cubes are non-rotated (logic 1), we perform a rotation (logic 0). If the first inputted cube is rotated (0), but the second is not (1), we choose to rotate the third (0), but, to get a less expected result, if the first cube is non-rotated (1), and the second is (0), we rotate the third cube (0). If both cubes are rotated (0), we rotate again (0), to further increase variety. rotated, we rotate as well, to further increase variety. This can be expressed with an AND and NOT logic gate: cube 3 = cube 1 AND NOT (cube 2), presented in Table 1.

cube 1	cube 2	cube 3
1	1	0
0	1	0
1	0	1
0	0	0

Table 1: The proposed logic gate.

When we provide a balanced superposition of states as input (as using the Hadamard gate), and we implement this logic gate within a quantum circuit, then the result is not deterministic but probabilistic. The quantum circuit implementing the logic gate of Table 1, for the case of two 1 states, is shown in Figure 1. The inputted states of

the first two cubes are used to initialize the qubits q_0 and q_1 , respectively. The state of the third cube is left blank, waiting for the information: “do the rotation” or “not do the rotation.” The core of the circuit is comprised within the vertical dashed bars. It contains a conditional NOT gate (CNOT) and a Toffoli gate (CCNOT). Their result goes into the third qubit, q_2 , providing hint for the operation to perform on the third cube. The result of the measurement operation is then stored into a classic bit, c_3 . The circuit is run 1024 times with an IBM quantum computer accessed remotely, getting a histogram of the frequency with which each result is obtained. For our application, we consider the most likely state.

Figure 1: The proposed quantum circuit (within the dashed vertical bars).

For our application, we considered three tests, leading respectively to three parts of our composition. The cases are described in Table 2. The first column presents the initialization of q_0, q_1 . The second column presents the pitch to play before (on the two first cubes) and after (on the third cube). The comma separates notes performed one after the other, while the dash indicates two notes performed simultaneously, as bichords.

initial choices	notes to play
(1, 1)	(C, D) → (E, B)
(0, 1)	(C, E-B) → (A-E)
(1/2, 0)	(C, D-E) → (A-D-B, C-E)

Table 2: The performed tests.

The sequences in the second column of Table 2 were played on the CubeHarmonic, recorded, and used as starting material for the overall composition. Considering the default configuration of the HyperCubeHarmonic shown in Figure 2, we can summarize our results. We can now summarize our results.

Test 1. Unchanged input configuration; from the quantum measurement: more likely to suggest “change”. So I perform a rotation involving the third cube (and the adjacent ones). (Cube 1 Do, cube 2 Re) → Cube 3 Mi-Sol (bichord). Notes: (Do, Re) → Mi-Sol.

Test 2. Input configuration: first cube rotated (and the adjacent). From the quantum simulation: very likely to suggest a new rotation. (Do, Mi-Si) → (La-Mi).

Test 3. Input configuration: undetermined, rotated. Result of the measurement: equiprobability of rotation (Do, Re-Mi) → 2nd cube La, Re, Si; 3rd cube Do-Mi.

Figure 2: The default CubeHarmonic configuration, with Cube 1, pink, C; Cube 2, orange, D; Cube 3, green, E; Cube 4, white, F; Cube 5, yellow, G; Cube 6, blue, A; Cube 7, red, B; Cube 8, violet, C one octave higher.

Figure 3: Test 1: configuration of the first and second cube, and choice of rotation for the third one.

Figure 4: Test 2: configuration of the first and second cube, and choice of rotation for the third one.

The sequences resulting from Test 1, 2, and 3 were then exported to Bitwig via LoopBack for sound editing. Further sequences were obtained playing the pitch of each test in a more free order, to be used later in the shared improvisation. Figure 2 shows the default configuration of the HyperCubeHarmonic. The preparation of musical material is shown in Figures 6 and 7.

3.2 The recording sessions, and the other instruments

As previously explained, a remotely-accessed IBM quantum computer was used as a decision-making helper to

Figure 5: Test 3: configuration of the first and second cube, and choice of rotation for the third one.

Figure 6: Audio from the HyperCubeHarmonic caught in LoopBack and sent to Bitwig, where it is edited.

Figure 7: Thematic editing of the sequences before using them as structure of the 3-part improvisation.

maximise 4D-CubeHarmonic chord variation.

A set of 3 chord variations was recorded directly from the web browser using Loopback (an audio routing software) into Bitwig (a digital audio workstation (DAW) designed for music production). The audio engine used for 4D-CubeHarmonic produced synthesised sounds which were very short. The chord sequences could only be triggered via a computer mouse (precluding musical playability), so the chord sequences were edited. A reverb plugin was applied to the final resulting audio to enable chord sequences to flow more naturally from one to another.

During the performance, these three chord se-

quences served as improvisational prompts, providing cues for tempo, structure, and pitch to other FLO performers. Figure 8 shows the geographic distribution of the performers and the instruments they played. The performers then created a telematic improvisational composition that complemented the sound synthesis produced by the 4D-CubeHarmonic through the addition of acoustic and prepared instruments, voice, live electronics, environmental loops, synthesisers and the Web Audio instrument Playsound.space. The composition spectrogram (Figure 9) shows the distribution of frequencies over time, where the most importance sequences where the HyperCubeHarmonic (HCH) plays are highlighted. The first chord sequence produced by 4D-CubeHarmonic can be seen at the beginning and at different points in time as the performance progresses, and the chord sequence returns as inspiration for free improvisation. The harmonic content, combined with percussion and noise components without a rhythm grid constraint (which is typical in free improvisation), can also be observed. FLO performers connected online using SonoBus (a Networked Music Performance platform), streaming audio from Italy, Croatia, Brazil, Australia, Poland and Spain to create ‘Telematic City Jam - Glasgow’. The final mix was recorded in SonoBus as a reference track, alongside locally-captured streams of individual performers. The audio was uploaded to a shared online archive so that the performance could be re-assembled, mixed and mastered offline without any artifacts and audio glitches that sometimes occur during telematic performances. The final mix was broadcast on 87.9 FM as part of the Radiophrenia 2025 festival, which took place in Glasgow, Scotland from 7th - 20th April, 2025. The resulting composition is an example of a novel way to create a Networked Music Performance, incorporating computer science, mathematics, and quantum physics.

4 Discussions

We presented a musical piece, in form of a networked remote improvisation, based on quantum-assisted composition from quantum algorithms specifically designed for the piece. The results of a quantum circuit measurement were mapped into a choice of rotations on the HyperCubeHarmonic, and the obtained musical sequences constituted the themes of the three sections of the improvisation.

This project blends quantum computing, new-instrument exploration, and NMP. The performance also involved synthesisers and acoustic instruments, performed by members of the Female Laptop Orchestra (FLO). The use of IBM runs influenced the creative process from the beginning, requiring the definition of a mapping between more likely states and musical rotations on the CubeHarmonic. As a compositional choice, the quantum-based sequences were used as starting themes and initial harmonic material.

Thus, the quantum-based sequences deeply influenced the first choices of performers, at least at the beginning of each of the three sections of the composition. The choice of how to use such an initial material, how to de-

Figure 8: Map of the geographic distribution of the FLO performers, with the instruments played.

Figure 9: Annotated spectrogram of the piece.

velop it, how to progressively add more pitches enriching the harmonic texture, and which rhythmic patterns to create, were all artistic choices of the performers, mutually listening to and influencing each other.

Further blendings of new techniques and traditional instrumental technique will help expand FLO’s audio-visual ‘vocabulary’ through utilising Web Audio, the Internet of Musical Things, AI, Quantum Computer Music, higher-order ambisonics, projection mapping and XR and exploring the following areas that could further advance FLO’s NMP framework: Real-time spatialisation and visualisation (enhancing the ‘in-person audience’ experience through audio spatialisation and visualisation). Live-streaming with Higher Order Ambisonics (HOA) audio and 360-degree video (enhancing the ‘virtual audience’ experience by utilising advancements in capturing and streaming immersive audio-visual content). Recording and post-production (evaluating tools for recording, post-production, and archiving the content generated from FLO performances so that it can be experienced by a broader audience (both physically and virtually) later). Utilising a collaborative, practice-based approach, FLO aims to identify novel streaming technologies and compositional tools and techniques, integrate these tools into the FLO project workflow and evaluate their usefulness within the context of Networked Music Performance (NMP).

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